

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT FACTORS ON HEALTH INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Health institutions try to develop strategies to meet the healthcare needs of the community effectively and efficiently, but they also endeavor to preserve their place in the market. However, an accurate analysis and understanding of environmental factors and establishing feedback channels are essential to be able to develop these strategies. In addition, by identifying environmental factors, health institutions can determine their weaknesses and strengths to eliminate the factors that may pose a threat and develop new opportunities.

The purpose of this study is to examine and classification of the external environmental factors affecting health institutions. We base our discussion of the external environmental factors on Lynch's classification of these factors, namely, political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, and legal environmental factors. Furthermore, we discuss the concept of environmental uncertainty, which is very important for health institutions, from Duncan's point of view.

Keywords: External Environmental Factors, Environmental Uncertainty

INTRODUCTION

Health institutions operate in a continuously changing dynamic environment with threatening uncertainties, as a result of which managerial mistakes may have serious consequences. Hence, health institutions' managers must constantly monitor the external environment of the institution, assess any potential threats and opportunities that may arise, and take timely and necessary precautions. This is because health institutions can endure and succeed to the extent that their managers are able to take advantage of environmental opportunities and shield their institutions against environmental threats.

The growth of health companies to enormous sizes, the use of new technologies in diagnosis and treatment, the internationalization of competition, changes in the way that society uses health services, changes in the financial instruments used, and increasing political pressure are among the developments that have made the relationship between health institutions and the environment even more important.

Health institutions can develop vigorous, realistic, evidence-based, and implementable strategies for the future to the extent that they understand their environments. With such strategies, they can gain an advantage in competition and ensure their continued existence.

In order to carry on their operations, health institutions must be able to accurately analyze their environments and environmental factors. That is, health institutions should conduct a thorough analysis of the political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, legal, epidemiological, international, and natural environmental conditions they face. The fact that health institutions operate in a constantly changing environment implies that managers must cope with environmental uncertainties. Thus, managers must develop proper approaches to reduce this uncertainty.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to thoroughly examine external environmental factors of health institutions. In addition, we aim to determine what the concept of external environmental factors means and implies for health institutions, and to see how different researchers working on health institutions discuss the concept of external environmental factors. We address the topic along similar lines with Lynch's labelling of external environmental factors referred to as PESTEL (acronym for political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal analysis). In addition, we attempt to analyze the external environmental factors developed by Richard Roomer, including political environmental factors, economic environmental factors, socio-cultural environmental factors, technological environmental factors, natural environmental factors, and legal environmental factors.

Since the service boundaries of health institutions have reached a global level, we also add epidemiological environmental actors and international environmental factors to our inquiry into the external factors of health institutions. Furthermore, we try to seek to conceptualize the journey of health institutions from a simple and stable environment to a complex and uncertain environment.

METHODOLOGY

In accordance with the purpose of the study, we conduct a detailed and systematic review of the related literature. We provide a general assessment of the main findings of the literature regarding external environment factor and environmental uncertainty concepts and discuss what these concepts signify for the health institutions in a comprehensive manner.

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ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AFFECTING HEALTH INSTITUTIONS

In order to be successful and continue their operations, health institutions must adapt to the environment, create feedback mechanisms to monitor and understand the environment, and design strategies that can respond to environmental changes. However, developing strategies that are applicable for being able to deal with environmental changes first and foremost requires identifying the external environmental conditions and environmental factors that affect the health institution. Health institutions are exposed to an extremely wide variety of environmental impacts because of the exceptionally broad nature of the concept of health.²

As illustrated in Figure 1, the external environment of health institutions can be classified into two groups, namely, the general environment and the task environment. The general environment includes all factors that directly or indirectly affect the health institution. On the other hand, the task environment consists of factors that directly affect the internal environment, activities, and performance of the health institution. Hence, the relative effects of factors in the task environment can be measured to some extent using appropriate indicators. An example of a task environment factor is the maximum amount of additional fees that can be collected from patients by private health institutions. In Turkey, according to a Council of Ministers Decree published in the Official Gazette on October 12, 2013, the maximum amount of additional fees that can be collected from patients by private health institutions through a contract with the Social Security Institution (SSI) was increased from 90% to 200%. A hospital manager can estimate the effect of this rise in the 'difference rate' on the number of patients served and revenues.

General environment includes the task environment; however, managers must pay more attention to the task environment as it is more closely related to and directly affects the health institution. We can explain the difference between the general environment and the task

environment with a simple example. Law (legislation) is a binding general environmental factor, that is, health institutions must perform their activities in accordance with legal rules. However, while some legislations within the legal system (such as Turkish Armed Forces Internal Service Law, and Inheritance and Inheritance Tax Law) does not directly affect health institutions, some other legislations (such as Health Practice Directive, Social Security and General Health Insurance Law, and Private Hospital Regulations) and amendments in these legislations have a substantial and direct influence on health institutions. To be precise, while the legal system in general constitutes the general environment, the legislations aimed at regulating and governing the health system make up the task environment.

The general environment and task environment influence the internal environment and activities of the health institutions. Internal environmental factors are under the control of management. That is, management can rearrange internal environmental conditions (e.g., they can reorganize the organization structure of the institution or adjust the clinical information system) in response to changing external environment conditions.

In the literature on strategic management, the external environment consists of environmental factors abbreviated as PESTEL (Lynch, 2006:84). These factors are:

- Political environmental factors,
- Economic environment,
- Socio-cultural environmental factors,
- Technological environmental factors,
- Environmental (Natural environmental) factors, and
- Legal environmental factors.

In addition to the environmental factors listed above, epidemiological environment conditions have also significant influence on the health institutions (Fisk, 1994:316). Also, the international environmental conditions have also gained importance as health institutions have begun to provide services on a global scale.

² The World Health Organization (WHO) defines health not only as the absence of disease or disability, but also as a state of complete physical, social, and mental well-being. From this perspective, it can be seen that many factors influence individual and public health. These factors, which are also considered as inputs for health, are generally grouped into four main categories: 1) Environment (physical, biological,

socio-cultural environment), 2) Behavior (smoking, alcohol consumption, etc.), 3) Genetics (inherited characteristics from birth), and 4) Health services. These four fundamental factors are influenced by the economic, political, and socio-cultural conditions of the country. Therefore, healthcare administrators aiming to improve the individuals and public's health cannot ignore the factors that affect health.

Figure 1. External Environment of Health institutions

The components of the Roemer model previously discussed are consistent with the environmental factors listed above. That is, the task environment studied in the Roemer also covers the external environment factors that are directly related to the health institutions.

Political Environment

A country's political structure, including the health policies adopted by the government as well as policies related to economic and socio-cultural realms, has wide-ranging influence on public health and health institutions. Health reforms, mostly shaped by the political choices of governments, started to radically transform Turkey's health system in the 1990s, and intensified even further in 2000s.

A good example of health reforms is the green card project put in implementation in 1992. The purpose of Law No. 3816 published in the Official Gazette on July 3, 1992, on the Coverage of Medical Expenses of Citizens with No Payment Ability by the State through the Issuance of a Green Card, was to cover the medical expenses of Turkish citizens who are not covered by any social security institution and do not have the means to pay for healthcare services. That is, the green card project enabled low-income groups without healthcare coverage to access health services. The importance of the green card project for the current study was that it converted the potential healthcare demand of the poor into effective demand, that is, it led to a significant rise in the demand for health services in public and private sector health institutions. Likewise, a new regulation introduced in 2003 allowed workpeople to use private hospitals without a referral. These regulations have considerably raised the number of patients seeking healthcare at private hospitals.

Governments' regulations on service utilization and pricing (reimbursement) systems have had a considerable effect on the financial state and competitiveness of hospitals during the last three decades. During this period, governments have used service price controls as a means to maintain budget balances and improve efficiency in health services. For example, in 2006, in order to control health expenses, the government decided to switch from a fee-for-service model³ to a case-based payment model⁴. The transition to a case-based payment system resulted in a decrease in hospital revenues and obliged them to provide more cost-effective services. In addition, both public and private sector hospitals have been forced to implement operational strategies aimed at reducing unnecessary laboratory tests, imaging services, and hospital stays and increasing the number of patients actually requiring treatment to provide cost-effective services.

With the implementation of the case-based payment model, some hospitals have adopted a different strategy; they have not engaged in an agreement with the SSI, and targeted upper income groups. On the other hand, some hospitals have preferred to join in agreements based on specialty (such as cardiovascular surgery and oncology). Although there is a limited number of studies on the reform efforts in the health sector in Turkey and their impacts on hospitals, it can be argued that the reforms have had a positive impact on hospital performance (Kavuncubaşı et al., 2008).

Economic Environment

Another crucial environmental factor that affects health institutions is the economic environment. Health institutions are also, in essence, economic entities, and therefore, their strategies need to be formed in accordance with the economic conditions they face in their environments. Major variables indicating the economic conditions in health institutions' environment can be listed as below:

- National income and per capita national income.
- Economic growth rate,
- Size of public spending,
- Distribution of public and private health spending,
- Health spending as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP),
- Competition in the health sector,
- Development plans and programs,
- Employment and unemployment rates,
- Exchange rates,
- Health workforce plans,
- Inflation rates,
- Interest rates, and
- Central Bank interventions.

The general economic conditions of a country have substantial influences on almost all activities of health institutions. National income and specifically

per capita national income, above all, significantly affect individuals' demands for health services.⁵

The size of health expenses, per capita health expenses, and the share of health expenses in GDP are issues that governments focus on. Governments constantly exert pressure on both health insurance institutions and service providers (health institutions) to control health expenses. The increase in health expenses can indicate the presence of growth opportunities for health institutions, but it can also signal the possibility of serious price controls or cost limitations by the governments in the future.

Competition is another important economic environmental factor in the health sector. Health institutions must constantly monitor the strategies and behaviors of their competitors in order to gain a competitive advantage.

Exchange rates are another key economic environmental factor. A large portion of the resources used in health institutions are imported products. There is also a major dependency on medical technology. An İstanbul Chamber of Commerce report describes this dependency plainly as follows (ITO, 2009:15):

Turkey is technologically dependent on medical devices, equipment, and materials to a significant extent. The market for most medical materials, except for some basic consumables, is generally based on imports. Almost all medical devices, and a large portion of medical equipment and materials are imported. Medical equipment imports are rapidly increasing, while exports are decreasing proportionally. Turkey is a net importer in the medical devices and materials sector. The sector's imports were \$646 million in 2003 and exceeded \$1.6 billion in 2007. There is a considerable increase in exports as well, but the export-import coverage ratio is only around 10%. The sector' imports come mostly from the US, Germany, Japan, Italy, China, the Netherlands, Ireland, and Malaysia.

A similar situation is also observed in the pharmaceutical sector (AİFD, 2012: 52):

Turkey meets 51% of its pharmaceutical needs through imports. The value of Turkey's pharmaceutical imports increased from \$3.04 billion in 2006 to \$4.7 billion in 2011, corresponding to an average annual increase of 9.1%. The volume of imports in the same period grew by an average of 15% per year and reached 422 million boxes from 180 million boxes. As a result, the trade deficit of the pharmaceutical sector rose to \$4.13 billion in 2011 from \$2.72 billion in 2006.

The above observations clearly show that the rise in foreign exchange rates naturally leads to an increase in costs for the health institutions. Therefore, health institutions' managers must closely follow exchange rate fluctuations and analyze their effects on service costs.

Interest rate is another vital economic environmental factor. Health institutions following growth strategies may need financial means to make new investments or renew outdated technology. The financial

³ In the fee-for-service model, each service provided to patients is invoiced separately.

⁴ In the case-based payment model, a fixed fee is paid per patient regardless of the number of services provided to the patient.

⁵ The impact of environmental factors on the demand for health services is discussed in a separate subheading in this section.

resources can be obtained from banks and other credit institutions at a certain cost (interest). The interest burden of health institutions varies according to the interest rate. Total interest expenses directly affect renewal and expansion decisions.

The inflation rate is probably one of the most important economic environmental factors that affects health institutions. Inflation has a direct influence on the financial performance of health because it leads to an increase in the cost of inputs (pharmaceuticals, medical supplies, etc.).

Employment and unemployment rates are also a matter of significance for health institutions. High employment rate leads to an increase in the insured population. In turn, an increase in the share of insured population raises the demand for health services. Therefore, when deciding the location of a health institution, factors such as the insured population ratio or the number of insured population are taken into consideration (Özcan, 2009).

Socio-Cultural Environment

Health institutions, specifically those operating in other foreign countries, must examine the socio-cultural characteristics of the country to determine what services to offer and in what manner. Examples of these socio-cultural attributes, that is, factors (variables) that must be covered in the analysis of the socio-cultural environment are presented below:

- Size of population,
- Marriage and divorce distribution,
- Schooling rate,
- Age and gender distribution of the population,
- Population growth rate,
- Lifestyle and trends in lifestyle differentiation,
- Changes in consumer behavior,
- Education level of the society,
- Cultural level of the society, and
- Urbanization rate.

One can argue that, among the socio-cultural factors, the size of the country's population and the age distribution of the population are the most important factors influencing the demand for health services. In most of the countries, including Turkey, the elderly population (65+) increases with a rate higher than that of other age groups. In 2013, according to the Turkish Statistical Institute (TSI) statistics, the population growth rate in Turkey was 1.37%, while the elderly population growth rate was approximately 2.6 times higher, at 3.62% (TUIK, 2014).⁶ It is known that the frequency of chronic and comorbid diseases increases in parallel with the aging of the population. Because the population and the age distribution of the population affect the demand for health services, managers of health institutions must analyze the demographics of the population they serve, predict which diseases are likely to occur with what frequency in the short, medium, and long term, and develop strategies and execution plans (bed planning, human resource planning, material planning, etc.) based on these predictions.

Moreover, since elderly patients need not only healthcare services but also social services (Rechel et al., 2009: X), managers of health institutions must plan a coordinated healthcare and social service provision. Besides, managers of health institutions should also develop alternative service delivery models, such as home care and nursing care centers, for the treatment of chronic diseases.

Technological Environment

Medical technology and diagnostic and treatment methods are developing at an incredible speed. Progress in medical technology and diagnostic and treatment methods results in an increase in demand for health services.⁷ In other words, new technologies and methods create new markets (new patient groups) and opportunities. Therefore, hospitals can gain a competitive advantage if they closely follow the developments in medical technology and diagnostic and treatment methods and try to put them in use before their rivals.

Technological developments have brought about significant improvements in service quality. For example, the success rate of cataract surgery using the phacoemulsification (PHACO) technique is considerably higher than that of traditional surgical methods. Due to the successful results of the PHACO technique, a large portion of cataract surgeries are now being performed with this technique. Hence, patients naturally prefer this new technique and use hospitals that apply this technique. Furthermore, the developments in medical technology and diagnostic and treatment methods have made healthcare services more secure in the eyes of patients and increased the frequency of use of healthcare services by the population that was delaying their healthcare needs due to fear or anxiety. For instance, open Magnetic Resonance (MR) technology allows people with claustrophobic to benefit from MR services. In addition, diagnostic and treatment errors (malpractice) have hugely decreased in parallel with technological developments. On the other hand, the use of new technologies requires substantial and continuous investment in research and development, which leads to an increase in service costs.

Health institutions publicize medical technologies they use in their websites to inform the public and expand their market share. With the widespread use of mass communication tools, the public has become aware of developments in medical technology and medicine and taken into account these developments when choosing a health institution for health services.

Legal Environment

Like all other businesses, both public and private health institutions must also abide by countries' legal rules (laws, regulations, decrees, etc.) in their operations. That is, the legal environment affects almost all the activities of health institutions. For example, in Turkey, the establishment of private hospitals, personnel employment, physicians-doctors employment, organizational structure and service standards of hospitals, service charges demanded from patients, and

leads patients to demand that technology or the method. However, there is a two-way causality, that is, the success of a new technology or method also depend on the increase in demand created by this new technology and the method.

⁶ <http://www.tuik.gov.tr/PreHaberBultenleri.do?id=16057>

⁷ According to Cutler and McClellan (2001), new medical technology has a demand-increasing effect (an expansion effect). The success of a new technology or treatment method

the manner of service delivery are regulated by the Regulation on Private Hospitals, Labor Law, the Law on Full-Time Work of University and Health Personnel, Social Security and General Health Insurance Law, and the Patient Rights Regulation, respectively.

Health institutions can face serious sanctions for managerial decisions and actions that are not in compliance with legal regulations. For instance, private hospitals can start their operations only if they have already employed at least half of the specified number of clinicians: They must also complete employing required number of personnel within two years from the date they start operating. In addition, if a private hospital has less than four specialist doctors, its operation is suspended for a period of two years. Most importantly, if the private hospital cannot resolve the shortage of specialist doctors at the end of this period, its license is cancelled in accordance with Private Hospital Regulation Article 6.

Health institutions with a strategy serving globally must also carry out their activities in accordance with international laws, trade regulations and bilateral and multilateral agreements between countries, in addition to domestic legal rules.

Natural Environment

Health institution managers should also take into account natural environmental conditions in developing and executing their strategies. There are two main reasons for considering natural environmental conditions in health institutions. First and foremost, the natural environment is a sustainability matter. Health institutions must carefully examine natural environmental conditions such as probability of earthquake, flood risk, and climate conditions in their location choice. Secondly, the natural environment exerts a substantial effect on the health status of the community over time.

Epidemiological changes

When developing their strategies and plans, health institution managers need to focus primarily on the health needs of the community and identify the health services that will meet these needs (Zelman and McLaughlin, 1990). The health needs of the community are determined through epidemiological research. Epidemiology is the branch of medical science studying the health needs of the community through investigating the transmission and control of diseases. Disease, disability, injury, and other health problems in the community create health needs and demand for health services. Epidemiologists try to determine the health needs of the community by analyzing the factors that influence the emergence, degree, and consequences of the health-related problems. That is, the fundamental aim of epidemiology is to identify the factors that influence the health needs of the community and to control and eliminate these factors to improve the health status of the community (Oleske, 2002:3). It must be emphasized that the fundamental mission of all health institutions is to provide services that meet the health needs of the community. However, the epidemiological characteristics of the community change over time; that is, while the incidence rate of some diseases increases, the incidence rate of others decreases. Hence, health institution managers should be aware that the demographic characteristics and disease structure of the community

may change and closely monitor these changes. Managers who are unaware of epidemiological changes will not be able to respond to the needs of the community effectively (Jeager, 2002: 99).

Epidemiological data is one of the most crucial inputs for the strategic management process because the health status and health needs of the population constitute the basis of strategic management. Epidemiological data also guides managers on which markets the health institution should target. In this case, the concept of market usually refers to a group or community. In other words, the concept of market denotes a community, a group of community, organizations and/or individuals that the health institution plans to serve. From an epidemiological perspective, the market that the health institution aims to serve is called “at-risk population” (Jeager, 2002: 108).

International Environment

Competition in the health sector has begun to globalize. Wealthy individuals resort to developed countries to meet their health needs, while individuals in developed countries also turn to developing countries to meet their health needs in a more economical manner. For instance, it is estimated that half a million individuals from the United States received health services in Mexico and South American countries. In addition to getting a better healthcare service, one main reason for individuals having health services in foreign countries is the cost of the service. For example, a heart surgery that costs \$4,000 in India costs \$30,000 in the United States (Herrick, 2007). The international movement of patients for the purpose of obtaining medical treatment is referred to as health tourism. Health tourism is considered to be an important opportunity for health institutions. Governments in most countries provide incentives such as financial support for overseas market entry, bureaucratic support for certification process, and consulting to health institutions and intermediary organizations to promote health tourism. Detailed information on the health tourism incentives in Turkey can be found in the communique titled Support for the Promotion of Services Trade that Generates Foreign Exchange published by the Ministry of Economy in 2012/4.

On the other hand, the international environment is not limited to health tourism. Major health institutions also establish diagnostic units (outpatient treatment centers) and hospitals abroad as part of their market development (expansion of the service area) strategy. Health institutions that provide services on an international scale must be well-informed about the economic, socio-cultural, legal, and epidemiological characteristics of the country where they provide health services, in addition to global economic and financial developments.

ENVIRONMENTAL UNCERTAINTY

The main factor that leads managers to engage with the external environment is the uncertainty created by the environment. Lack of information is the main source of uncertainty. For example, we do not experience uncertainty about the population of Turkey in 2023; because the population of Turkey is increasing at a relatively stable rate. Since the rate of population growth

is approximately constant, we can predict the population in 2023 with a high accuracy. On the other hand, we face uncertainty about what the exchange rates will be in the next three months. The root cause of this uncertainty is the lack of sufficient information, and sometimes the lack of sufficient time to access this information. Therefore, we can define environmental uncertainty as “managers not having sufficient information about environmental factors when making decisions, and not having necessary time to obtain this information” (Daft, 2010).

According to Duncan (1972), environmental uncertainty is closely related to the number of environmental factors affecting the health institution and the rate of change of these factors. The environment becomes more complex as the number of environmental factors affecting a health institution rises. In addition, the environmental complexity will increase further at the same time as degree of heterogeneity of these factors. We can explain this with a simple example. Assume that we have 5, 10, and 20, 50, and 100 Turkish lira bills in our pocket. We can easily and quickly say in total how much money we have in our pocket. On the other hand, if we have 5 British pounds, 10 US dollars and 20 Turkish lira bills, it is not possible for us to immediately calculate how much money we have in our pocket in Turkish lira terms. We will have to know pound-lira and dollar-lira exchange rates and convert pound and dollar into lira. Although we have five bills in the first example, we made an easy calculation. In the second example, although we have 3 bills in our pocket, we had to spend time and effort to do the calculation. We can divide the environment into two sections in terms of complexity: simple environment and complex environment. In the simple environment there are

a few homogeneous factors affecting the health institution. Health institutions in districts or small-town centers operate in a simple environment. Health institutions in complex environments are affected by many environmental factors with a high degree of heterogeneity.

The second factor affecting environmental uncertainty is the rate of change of environmental factors. The rate of change of environmental factors can be fast or slow. If the rate of change of an environmental factor is low, it makes it easier for us to know how that factor will vary over time. For example, as mentioned above, the rate of population growth in Turkey our country is relatively constant. And because the rate of population growth is constant, we can easily depict the time path of the population. However, it is difficult to forecast the exchange rates, gauge how intense competition will become, foresee which technologies will be developed, foretell which diseases will emerge and which ones will vanish, and predict what health policies the government will implement. If environmental factors do not change at all or change in a predictable and slow manner, this environment is called a stable environment. On the other hand, if environmental factors change very fast and unpredictably, this type of environment is called a dynamic environment (Duncan, 1972).

When we bring together environmental complexity and the rate of environmental change in a conceptual framework, we come up with four types of environments as shown in Figure 2. These four types of environments are:

1. Simple - stable environment
2. Complex - stable environment
3. Simple - unstable environment
4. Complex - unstable environment

Figure 2. Types of Environments According to Degree of Uncertainty

NOTE: The numbers in parentheses reflect the degree of uncertainty.

According to the framework presented in Figure 6; in a simple-stable environment, uncertainty is very low. The number of environmental factors affecting the health institution is low and these factors change

slowly. That is to say that the degree of uncertainty perceived by the managers of the health institutions operating in this type of environment is very low. Health institutions operating in a complex-stable environment are exposed to more environmental uncertainty than in

a simple-stable environment. These institutions must deal with many environmental factors, and monitor and evaluate them. However, the rate of change of these factors is very slow, so the degree of uncertainty perceived by the managers is also low.

In a simple-unstable environment, uncertainty is higher than in both simple-stable and complex-stable environments. Although the number of environmental factors is low in a simple-unstable environment, uncertainty is high due to the rapid change of these factors.

The environment with the highest degree of uncertainty is the complex-unstable environment. In this type of environment, a large number of environmental factors affect the health institution, and these factors change very rapidly.

CONCLUSION

Health institutions need to adapt to the environment, create feedback mechanisms for monitoring and defining the environment, and design strategies that can respond to environmental changes to be successful and continue to operate.

Health institutions are exposed to an extremely wide variety of environmental impacts because of the exceptionally broad nature of the concept of health. These factors, which are also inputs for health, are the environment (physical, biological, socio-cultural environment), behavior (smoking, alcohol addiction, etc.), genetics (inherited traits acquired at birth), and health services.

As competition in healthcare organizations increases, we can say that the boundaries of service delivery have reached a global level. Therefore, we must also add international environmental factors to the environmental factors that affect health institutions.

Health institution need to cope with many environmental factors, including political environmental factors, economic environmental factors, socio-cultural environmental factors, technological environmental factors, natural environmental factors, legal environmental factors, epidemiological environmental factors, and international environmental factors. Given the large number and heterogeneity of environmental factors, health institutions must develop data-based, realistic, and implementable strategies.

Uncertainty stemming from lack of information rises with the number and speed of environmental factors affecting health institutions. As the environment health institutions exposed broadens, they also moving from a simple-stable environment where uncertainty is at a minimum, to a complex-unstable environment where uncertainty is at its highest.

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